

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

“INFLUENCE OF NSAIDS ON BLOOD PRESSURE IN HYPERTENSIVE PATIENTS UNDER TREATMENT: A CROSS SECTIONAL STUDY”

Cherian Anish¹, Mathew Cherry¹, Geevarughese Merlin¹, T.Chaitanya Kumar^{2*}

¹Department of Pharmacy Practice, Bapuji Pharmacy College, Davangere, Karnataka, India.

²Department of Pharmacy Practice, Bapuji Pharmacy College, Davangere, Karnataka, India.

ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 28/01/2018

Available online

28/02/2018

Keywords

NSAIDs,
Anti-hypertensives,
Blood Pressure.

ABSTRACT

Raised blood pressure is one of the leading risk factors for global mortality and is estimated to have caused 9.4 million deaths. There are chances of using anti-hypertensives and NSAIDs together with increasing age for a long time to treat many diseases. The objective of this study was to determine the change in blood pressure in hypertensive patients on Anti-hypertensives after consumption of NSAIDs. The cross-sectional analytical study was conducted for a period of 6 months. In our study out of 70 NSAID users, 55.71% were males and 44.29% were females and from 140 NSAID non users, 61.43% were males and 38.57% were females. 26.67% of patients were having Diabetes mellitus as a comorbid condition along with hypertension. From all the covariates studied, light physical activity was 1.44 and moderate physical activity was 1.06 times more likely to have this influence than vigorous physical activity. A difference of 3.67mmHg in systolic blood pressure was noted between NSAID users and non-users. When comparing Amlodipine, Enalapril and Telmisartan, Telmisartan was the only drug that showed a significant difference in blood pressure after consumption of NSAIDs i.e, 8.35mmHg. Mostly prescribed NSAIDs were Diclofenac followed by Etoricoxib and Aspirin. We found that NSAIDs may increase blood pressure and may blunt the effects of many anti-hypertensives. The small increase in systolic blood pressure associated with NSAIDs seen in this study may not affect a physician's decision to change the therapy, however in long term, such an increase would be associated with significant comorbidity consequences.

Corresponding author

Mr. T.Chaitanya Kumar

Assistant Professor
Department of Pharmacy Practice,
Bapuji Pharmacy College,
Davangere -577004,
Karnataka, India.
+91 9845683133
chaitu.vishu@gmail.com

Please cite this article in press as **Mr. T.Chaitanya Kumar et al.** “Influence of Nsaids on Blood Pressure in Hypertensive Patients Under Treatment: A Cross Sectional Study”. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2018;8(02).

Copy right © 2018 This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Indo American journal of Pharmaceutical Research, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

INTRODUCTION

Hypertension is defined as a systolic blood pressure equal to or above 140 mmHg and/or diastolic blood pressure equal to or above 90 mmHg. Normal levels of both systolic and diastolic blood pressure are particularly important for the efficient function of vital organs such as the heart, brain and kidneys and for overall health and well-being. Consumption of food containing too much salt and fat, and not eating enough fruits and vegetables, harmful levels of alcohol use, physical inactivity and lack of exercise, poor stress management are all considered as behavioral risk factors for the development of hypertension. [1]

Cardiovascular diseases are found to be the most common cause of death in the world, and uncontrolled hypertension is a sign of such poor outcomes. [2] Globally, cardiovascular disease accounts for approximately 17 million deaths a year, nearly one third of the total population. [1] Worldwide, raised blood pressure is estimated to cause 7.5 million deaths, that is approximately 12.8% of the total annual deaths. [4] The overall prevalence of hypertension in India is 29.8% .[5]The prevalence of hypertension in Karnataka is found to be 43.3% in a study conducted by Kasthubha medical college, Manipal.[6] High blood pressure levels have been shown to be positively related to the risk for stroke and coronary heart disease.[7] Use of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs in patients treated with anti-hypertensive medication can lead to destabilization of blood pressure control and other cardio-renal events. [11]

Various large epidemiological studies and meta-analyses of clinical trials have been conducted to assess the effect of NSAIDs on blood pressure in patients treated with anti-hypertensives. In these studies, NSAIDs were not always associated with an increase in blood pressure, and the maximum increase was 6.2 mmHg. [12]

Anti-hypertensives and NSAIDs are frequently co-prescribed, in up to 12% of community dwelling elderly. [13]

Previous studies on NSAIDs and hypertension have given out conflicting results and examined relationships between NSAID usage in non-treated and treated patients.

The effect of NSAIDs on the incidence of hypertension has been previously investigated. But, little information is available about the magnitude of changes in blood pressure in populations of patients taking antihypertensive medications regularly. The effect of NSAIDs on blood pressure has been investigated in clinical trials, but not observational studies, which are more representative to real-world clinical settings.

Based on our limited literature review, we found that almost all the studies are done outside India. We would like to find whether there is any risk in Indian population.

To address this issue, we would like to examine the association between use of the analgesic classes and risk of hypertension among subjects with a previous history of hypertension who are on treatment.

METHODOLOGY

STUDY SITE

The study was conducted in Inpatient and Outpatient Medicine and Orthopaedics Departments of SSIMS&RC, Davangere, Karnataka, a 400 bedded hospital.

STUDY DESIGN

A cross-sectional analytical study

STUDY DURATION

The study was carried out for a period of 6 months.

SAMPLE SIZE

The sample size for the study was calculated using the following equation;

$$n = \left[\frac{z_{\alpha/2} \sigma}{E} \right]^2$$

$z_{\alpha/2}$ is critical value, 1.96

σ is the population standard deviation

n is the sample size

E difference between observed samples

According to Sheridan et al standard deviation was 15 and difference found was 2mmHg.

Using the above stated equation the sample size calculated was 216.09

Total sample size: 200

SELECTION CRITERIA

The study will be carried out by considering the following inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Inclusion criteria

- Hypertensive patients with controlled blood pressure less than 140/90 mmHg on any one antihypertensive for a minimum period of 6 months.
- Patients who are on NSAID for pain relief.
- Patients of either sex within the age group of 20-60 years.
- Patients willing to participate.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with fluctuating BP
- Pregnant and lactating women
- Patients with other diseases such as ischemic heart disease, stroke, end organ damages, sleep apnea and any form of secondary hypertension.
- Patients with mental disorders, dementia or judicial disability.
- NSAID dosage forms other than oral.
- Patients in which changes are foreseen in usual dose drugs with effects on BP throughout the study (alpha blockers, tricyclic antidepressants, beta blockers in eye drops, sympathomimetic vasoconstrictor, other effervescent agents, hormonal contraceptives, corticosteroids, anabolic, erythropoietin, cyclosporine)

ETHICAL APPROVAL

Ethical approval was obtained from The Institutional Ethical Committee of Bapuji Pharmacy College, Davangere, Karnataka.

Data analysis

The collected data were coded and entered in Microsoft excel 2010 and then transferred to SPSS version 10.0. The added data was analysed with appropriate tests like t-test and multi-variate regression analysis to see the association between various parameters with p value 0.05 considered as significant.

RESULTS

After scrutinizing, using inclusion and exclusion criteria 210 patients were enrolled into the study. Out of 210 patients, 70 were users and 140 were non users of NSAIDs.

Table 1: Details of gender distribution, age group, education, occupation, family history, food habits, physical activity, sleeping time, duration of antihypertensive therapy, prescribing pattern of anti-hypertensive drugs.

Gender	NSAID users (n=70)	NSAID non users (n=140)	Total (n=210)
Males	39(55.71%)	86(61.43%)	125(59.52%)
Females	31(44.29%)	54(38.57%)	85(40.48%)
Age group			
21-30	2 (2.86%)	4(2.86%)	6(2.86%)
31-40	4 (5.71%)	26(18.57%)	30(14.29%)
41-50	23 (32.86%)	49(35.00%)	72(34.29%)
51-60	41 (58.57%)	61(43.57%)	102(48.57%)
Education			
Illiterate	22(31.43%)	33(23.57%)	55(26.19%)
Primary	20(28.57%)	48(34.28%)	68(32.38%)
Secondary	19(27.14%)	39(27.86%)	58(27.62%)
Graduate	9(12.86%)	20(14.29%)	29(13.81%)
Occupation			
Agriculture	18(25.71%)	31(22.14%)	49(23.33%)
Business	12(17.14%)	39(27.86%)	51(24.29%)
Government Employee	4(5.72%)	0(0%)	4(1.90%)
Unemployed	20(28.57%)	40(28.57%)	60(28.57%)
Self-Employee	14(20.00%)	21(15%)	35(16.67%)
Teacher	2(2.86%)	9(6.43%)	11(5.24%)
Family History			
Yes	35(50%)	71(50.71%)	106(50.48%)
No	35(50%)	69(49.29%)	104(49.52%)
Food habits			
Diet	Vegetarians	36(51.43%)	62(44.29%)

	Non-vegetarians	34(48.57%)	78(55.71%)
Use of extra salt	Yes	18(25.71%)	41(29.29%)
	No	52(74.29%)	99(70.71%)
Clinical variables			
Physical activity	Light	19(27.14%)	30(21.43%)
	Moderate	44(62.86%)	96(68.57%)
	Vigorous	7(10.00%)	14(10%)
Sleeping time	≤5 hours	8(11.43%)	18(12.86%)
	6-7 hours	48(68.57%)	100(71.43%)
	>7 hours	14(20.00%)	22(15.71%)
Duration of anti-hypertensive drug therapy			
≤6 months	27(38.57%)	75(53.57%)	102(48.57%)
>6 months	43(61.43%)	65(46.43%)	108(51.43%)
Diabetes Mellitus			
Yes	23(32.86%)	33(23.57%)	56(26.67%)
No	47(67.14%)	107(76.43%)	154(73.33%)
Drug Name			
Amlodipine 5mg	34(48.57%)	84(60%)	118(56.19%)
Atenolol 50mg	0(0%)	5(3.57%)	5(2.38%)
Clinidipine 5mg	0(0%)	1(0.71%)	1(0.48%)
Enalapril 2.5mg	6(8.57%)	12(8.57%)	18(8.57%)
Labetalol 100mg	2(2.86%)	0(0%)	2(0.95%)
Ramipril 2.5mg	0(0%)	5(3.57%)	5(2.38%)
Telmisartan 40mg	28(40%)	33(23.58%)	61(29.05%)

Table 1: Prescribing pattern of NSAIDs among the study population.

NSAID drug name	Total (n=70)
Aspirin	10(14.29%)
Diclofenac	22(31.43%)
Etoricoxib	18(25.71%)
Ibuprofen	4(5.71%)
Naproxen	8(11.43%)
Paracetamol	8(11.43%)

Table 2: Comparison of characteristics of NSAID and non-NSAID groups.

Characteristics	Mean±SD		t value	P value
	NSAID Users (n=70)	NSAID non users (n=140)		
Body weight (kg)	64.33±10.80	65.24±11.44	-0.567	0.572
Height (cm)	164.91±10.43	165.81±12.63	-0.544	0.587
Age (years)	51.47±7.74	48.94±8.51	2.164	0.032
BMI (kg/m ²)	23.58±3.35	24.1±8.69	-0.618	0.537

Table 3: Blood pressure in NSAID and non-NSAID users.

Blood Pressure (mmHg)	Mean±SD		t value	P value
	Users (n=70)	Non users (n=140)		
Systolic blood pressure (mm Hg)	141.71±10.55	138.03±8.90	2.510	0.013*
Diastolic blood pressure (mm Hg)	83.14±6.27	82.34±5.13	0.924	0.357

Table 4: Associated factors for the influence of NSAIDs on blood pressure in hypertensive patients under treatment.

Factors		Users (n=70)	Non users (n=140)	Odds ratio
Family history	Yes	35	71	0.97
	No	35	69	Ref
Physical activity	Light	19	30	1.44
	Moderate	44	96	1.06
	Vigorous	7	14	Ref
Alcohol	Non alcoholic	49	99	0.59
	Past	4	16	0.31
	Current	17	25	Ref
Smoking	Never	52	107	0.89
	Past	11	20	0.88
	Current	7	13	Ref
Dietary habits	Vegetarian	36	62	1.37
	Non vegetarian	34	78	Ref
Use of extra salt	Yes	18	41	0.81
	No	52	99	Ref
Sleeping time	≤ 5 hours	8	18	0.73
	6-7 hours	48	100	0.76
	>7 hours	14	22	Ref
Diabetes mellitus	Yes	23	33	1.63
	No	47	102	Ref

Table 5: Comparison of influence of NSAIDs on different antihypertensive drugs.

Anti-hypertensive drug	Mean±SD		t value	p value
	NSAID Users (n)	NSAID Non users (n)		
Amlodipine				
Systolic blood pressure	139.88±10.95(34)	138.26±8.85(84)	0.767	0.446
Diastolic blood pressure	83.53±7.73(34)	82.6±5.34(84)	0.644	0.522
Enalapril				
Systolic blood pressure	136.67±5.16(6)	140±6.03(12)	-1.219	0.247
Diastolic blood pressure	80±0(6)	82.50±4.52(12)	-1.915	0.082
Telmisartan				
Systolic blood pressure	145.14±10.52(28)	136.79±10.08(33)	3.150	0.002
Diastolic blood pressure	83.57±4.88(28)	81.51±4.42(33)	1.713	0.092

DISCUSSION

Anti-hypertensive and Non-Steroidal Anti-Inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are used to treat many common diseases. However, it has been suspected that interaction between these drugs exists. Here, we assessed the interactions between NSAIDs and several classes of anti-hypertensives.

In our study when considering gender wise distribution, among hypertensive patients males (59.52) were more when compared with females (40.48%). A similar observation was found in a study conducted by Ahmad A et.al where (63.3%) males and (36.7%) females had hypertension. [12]

Our study showed that greater number of patients came under the age group of 51-60(48.5%) followed by 41- 50(34.29%) which was similar in the study conducted by Mahajan H et.al. [14]

The majority of the patients in the present study had primary education (32.38%). This was similar to the study conducted by Mounica B et.al which showed that 32% and 46% of patients had primary education respectively. [16]

Most of our patients were unemployed (28.57%) in our study, which was similar to the study conducted by Mahajan H et.al which showed that 39.7% of their study population was either unemployed or unskilled. [14]

70.48% and 75.71% of the study subjects have never consumed alcohol nor smoked respectively. 9.52% and 14.76% had consumed alcohol and smoked in the past, whereas 20.0 % and 9.52% were current alcohol consumers and smokers respectively. A study conducted by Mounica B et.al showed that 51.72% and 44.82% were current smokers and alcoholics. [16]

The majority (71.90%) of our study subjects was not using extra salt when compared with the rest of the subjects (28.90%). Amrin Y Tadviet.al's study showed that 60.3% participants had extra salt in their diet. [18]

Present study had 66.67% of subjects to be engaged in moderate physical activity followed by 23.33% engaged in light physical activity. Aubert Let.al's study found that 36.4% of their subjects were engaged in light physical activity. [19]

Prescribing pattern of anti-hypertensives in our study subjects were Amlodipine 5 mg, Calcium Channel Blockers [CCB] (56.19%) followed by Telmisartan 40 mg, Angiotensin II Receptor Blockers [ARB] (29.05%) and Enalapril 2.5 mg, Angiotensin Converting Enzyme [ACEI] (8.57%). Similar results were found in a study conducted by Kamal Pandey et.al. [21]

Prescribing pattern analysis of NSAIDs in our study was found to be of the order: Diclofenac (31.43%) followed by Etoricoxib (25.71%) and Aspirin (14.29%). Manohar V R et.al conducted a study to analyse the prescribing patterns of NSAIDs in Dakshina Karnataka, district of South India and he found that 22% of prescription contains Paracetamol and Diclofenac each. [30]

In the current study, patients who received NSAIDs showed a 3.67mmHg increase in systolic blood pressure and 0.8 mmHg increase in diastolic blood pressure compared to those who were not. Similar to the current study, a study conducted by Cheiko Ishiguro et.al. [22]

The result of the current study may have some clinical implications. It has been reported that a decrease of 2.2 mmHg in SBP lowers mortality due to coronary heart disease by 4%. [19]

The small increase in systolic blood pressure associated with NSAIDs seen in this study may not affect a physician's decision to change the therapy, however in the long term, such an increase would be associated with significant comorbidity consequences. For example decrease in systolic blood pressure by just 2 mmHg lowers stroke mortality by 10% and ischemic heart disease mortality by 7%. [16]

Further studies are needed to assess the long term effects of such a small increase in blood pressure.

CONCLUSION

There are chances of using anti-hypertensives and NSAIDs together with increasing age for a long time to treat many common diseases. It has been suspected that interaction between these drugs exists. NSAIDs may increase blood pressure and may blunt the effect of many anti-hypertensives.

The present cross sectional study was carried out to examine the extent of interaction between NSAIDs and anti-hypertensives. This study provides an insight to various other covariates that are associated with this interaction. The study revealed that hypertension was prevalent in males compared to females.

1. In our study total of 210 patients were included and it was found that patients between age group of 51-60 had higher incidence of hypertension when compared to other age groups.
2. Most of our subjects in our study had primary education and most of the subjects were unemployed.
3. We found that more than half of the population in our study had family history of hypertension and Diabetes Mellitus was a comorbid condition for most the subjects.
4. In our study Amlodipine was the mostly prescribed anti-hypertensive drug, followed by Telmisartan and Enalapril. Among NSAIDs, Diclofenac was the mostly prescribed, followed by Etoricoxib and Aspirin.
5. In this study among anti-hypertensive patients who received NSAIDs showed a 3.67 mmHg increase in systolic blood pressure and 0.8 mmHg in diastolic blood pressure compared to those who were not. Hence, NSAIDs may attenuate the effect of anti-hypertensive drug. This is particularly important in long time treatment in elderly population
6. With regard to individual anti-hypertensive drug, increase in systolic blood pressure due to NSAID consumption was 8.35 mmHg and 1.62 mmHg in Telmisartan and Amlodipine users compared to non-users.
7. From all the covariates studied using multiple logistic regressions, light physical activity was 1.44 and moderate physical activity was 1.06 times more likely to have this influence than vigorous physical activity. The odds of interaction were 1.37 times higher among vegetarians when compared with non-vegetarians. The odds of interaction were 1.63 times more in diabetic patients compared to non-diabetes patients.

In conclusion we found that NSAIDs may increase blood pressure and may blunt the effects of many anti-hypertensives. The small increase in systolic blood pressure associated with NSAIDs seen in this study may not affect a physician's decision to change the therapy, however in long term, such an increase would be associated with significant comorbidity consequences

Conflict of interest:

There is no conflict of interest

REFERENCE

1. World Health Organization (WHO). A global brief on hypertension: silent killer, global public health crisis. People. 2017 Feb 22.
2. Yach D, Hawkes C, Gould CL, Hofman KJ. The global burden of chronic diseases: overcoming impediments to prevention and control. *Journal of the American Medical Association*. 2004 Jun 2; 291 (21): 2616-2622.
3. World Health Organization. Global health risks: mortality and burden of disease attributable to selected major risks. World Health Organization; 2009.
4. Anchala R, Kannuri NK, Pant H, Khan H, Franco OH, Di Angelantonio E, Prabhakaran D. Hypertension in India: a systematic review and meta-analysis of prevalence, awareness, and control of hypertension. *Journal of hypertension*. 2014 Jun 1; 32 (6): 1170-1177.
5. Rao CR, Kamath VG, Shetty A, Kamath A. High blood pressure prevalence and significant correlates: a quantitative analysis from coastal Karnataka, India. *International Scholarly Research Notices- Preventive Medicine*. 2012 Dec 3; 2013.
6. World Health Organization, International Society of Hypertension Writing Group. 2003 World Health Organization (WHO) /International Society of Hypertension (ISH) statement on management of hypertension. *Journal of hypertension*. 2003 Nov 1; 21 (11): 1983-1992.

7. Chobanian AV, Bakris GL, Black HR, Cushman WC, Green LA, Izzo Jr JL, Jones DW, Materson BJ, Oparil S, Wright Jr JT, Roccella EJ. The seventh report of the joint national committee on prevention, detection, evaluation, and treatment of high blood pressure: the JNC 7 report. *Journal of the American Medical Association*. 2003 May 21;289 (19): 2560-2571.
8. Weir MR. Renal effects of nonselective NSAIDs and coxibs. *Cleveland Clinic Journal Of Medicine*. 2002 Jan 1;69 (1): 53-58.
9. Whelton A, Fort JG, Puma JA, Normandin D, Bello AE, Verburg KM, Success VI Study Group. Cyclooxygenase-2-specific inhibitors and cardiorenal function: a randomized, controlled trial of celecoxib and rofecoxib in older hypertensive osteoarthritis patients. *American journal of therapeutics*. 2001 Mar 1; 8 (2): 85-95.
10. Baxter K. Stockley's drug interactions. Preston CL, editor. London: Pharmaceutical Press; 2010. 861-863.
11. Johnson AG, Simons LA, Simons J, Friedlander Y, McCallum J. Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs and hypertension in the elderly: a community-based cross-sectional study. *British journal of clinical pharmacology*. 1993 May 1;35 (5): 455-459.
12. Ahmad A, Ahmad MT. Assessment of knowledge, attitude and practice among diabetic patients attending a health care facility in North India. *Indian Journal of Basic and Applied Medical Research*. 2015;4(3):501-9.
13. Bavry AA, Khaliq A, Gong Y, Handberg EM, Cooper-DeHoff RM, Pepine CJ. Harmful effects of NSAIDs among patients with hypertension and coronary artery disease. *The American journal of medicine*. 2011 Jul 31;124 (7): 614-620.
14. Mahajan H, Kazi Y, Sharma B, Velhal GD. Assessment of KAP, risk factors and associated co-morbidities in hypertensive patients. *International Organization of Scientific Research-Journal of Dental and Medical Sciences*. 2012 Sep; 1 (2): 06-14
15. Deepa R, Shanthirani CS, Pradeepa R, Mohan V. Is the 'rule of halves' in hypertension still valid? Evidence from the Chennai Urban Population Study. *Journal of the Association of Physicians of India*. 2003 Feb 3; 51 (2): 153-157.
16. Mounica B. Study Of Knowledge, Attitude And Practice Of General Population Of Guntur Towards Silent Killer Diseases: Hypertension And Diabetes. *Value in Health*. 2015 Nov 1;18 (7): A398.
17. Pettersen BJ, Anousheh R, Fan J, Jaceldo-Siegl K, Fraser GE. Vegetarian diets and blood pressure among white subjects: results from the Adventist Health Study-2 (AHS-2). *Public health nutrition*. 2012 Oct 1;15 (10): 1909-1916.
18. Tadvī AY, Bandi JR. Study of prevalence of hypertension in young adult population of age group 20 to 40 years in an urban slum of Mumbai, Maharashtra, India. *International Journal Of Community Medicine And Public Health*. 2016 Dec 22;3 (12): 3325-3331.
19. Aubert L, Bovet P, Gervasoni JP, Rwebogora A, Waeber B, Paccaud F. Knowledge, attitudes, and practices on hypertension in a country in epidemiological transition. *Hypertension*. 1998 May 1;31 (5): 1136-1145.
20. Gottlieb DJ, Redline S, Nieto FJ, Baldwin CM, Newman AB, Resnick HE, Punjabi NM. Association of usual sleep duration with hypertension: the Sleep Heart Health Study. *SLEEP-NEW YORK THEN WESTCHESTER*. 2006 Aug 1; 29 (8): 1009.
21. Pandey K, Thakur PB, RamKumar K, Kumar P, Vishwanath BA. Drug use evaluation of antihypertensive drugs in the tertiary care hospital. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*. 2016; 6(9):6558-6568.
22. Ishiguro C, Fujita T, Omori T, Fujii Y, Mayama T, Sato T. Assessing the effects of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs on antihypertensive drug therapy using post-marketing surveillance database. *Journal of epidemiology*. 2008;18(3):119-124.
23. Sheridan R, Montgomery AA, Fahey T. NSAID use and BP in treated hypertensives: a retrospective controlled observational study. *Journal of human hypertension*. 2005 Jun 1;19 (6): 445-450.

54878478451180119

Submit your next manuscript to **IAJPR** and take advantage of:

Convenient online manuscript submission

Access Online first

Double blind peer review policy

International recognition

No space constraints or color figure charges

Immediate publication on acceptance

Inclusion in **Scopus** and other full-text repositories

Redistributing your research freely

Submit your manuscript at: editorinchief@iajpr.com

